

Complexes of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) with Bis-4-oxo(5,6-benz)-1,3-oxazine, a Quadridentate Schiff Base

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Complexes of nickel(II), copper(II) and cobalt(II) with Schiff base formed by condensation of anthranillic acid and glyoxal, have been synthesised and their physico-chemical properties are investigated using visible spectroscopy, magnetic susceptibility measurements and infrared spectroscopy. The solvent effect and ligation at fifth and sixth position on their geometry have been studied. The dioxygen intake at the metal center in cobalt complex has been established.

THE present investigation deals with synthesis of potential quadridentate ligand from anthranillic acid and glyoxal. The molecular models show that the ligand can wrap comfortably around divalent transition metals via two N and two O atoms to form square-planar complexes. It has been reported¹ that increase in $-N=CH-CH=N-$ chain induces sufficient distortion from planar towards tetrahedral geometry and spin multiplicity from 0 to 1, in a series of Ni^{II} complexes where the number of carbon atoms in the chain are 5 to 12. Positive spectral evidence and change in magnetic moment were observed on introduction of a base ligand in fifth axial position. The reversible uptake of oxygen is well evidenced by spectral change in the Co^{II} complexes.

Experimental

All reagents and solvents were of high purity or of analytical reagent grade and were used as such.

IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu IR 440 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a Shimadzu UV 240 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibilities in the solid state were measured at room temperature by the Gouy technique.

Synthesis of ligand: The ligand bis-4-oxo(5,6'-benz)-1,3-oxazine (hereafter referred to as BOBO) was synthesised by adding dropwise glyoxal (1.0 ml) to the ethanolic solution (20 ml) containing anthranillic acid (2.4 g) and stirring simultaneously for 1 h. The white product was washed with absolute alcohol and dried in an oven (80°), m.p. 182–84°.

Preparation of metal complexes: Template preparation of the metal complexes was accomplished by adding ethanolic solutions of the appropriate metal salts (nitrate/acetate) to a mixture of glyoxal and anthranillic acid (1 : 2 ratio) in ethanol. The Co^{II} complex was prepared under nitrogen atmosphere.

The complexes were washed with methanol and dried under reduced pressure (Table 1). They were air-stable, non-hygroscopic and insoluble in C_2H_5OH , THF, DMSO and CH_3CN .

Pyridine and imidazole adducts: The metal complexes of BOBO were refluxed in pyridine and the pyridine solution was concentrated under reduced pressure to crystallise out the pyridine adducts.

To a freshly prepared pyridine solution of the complexes, imidazole was added maintaining 1 : 1 complex-imidazole ratio. After stirring well the

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, AND PHYSICAL, DATA OF THE LIGAND AND COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)			μ_{eff} B.M.
		C	H	N	
Ligand	White	64.26 (64.86)	3.92 (4.05)	9.31 (9.45)	
CoBOBO	Light pink	54.1 (54.4)	2.71 (2.83)	7.75 (7.88)	2.34
Co BOBOPy	Pinkish brown	57.95 (58.34)	3.41 (3.47)	9.61 (9.72)	2.51
Co.BOBOImPy	Red	58.1 (57.60)	3.70 (4.80)	14.2 (14.0)	5.01
Cu.BOBO	Green	53.42 (53.69)	2.69 (2.74)	7.80 (7.88)	Dia.
Ni.BOBO	Light green	54.10 (54.43)	2.74 (2.83)	8.10 (7.93)	Dia.

pyridine was allowed to evaporate when the imidazole adducts crystallised out. The complexes were washed with acetone and dried under reduced pressure.

Oxygen adduct: Oxygen was bubbled through the pyridine solution of the cobalt(II) complex for 30 min and the spectrum was recorded. A new characteristic band similar to octahedral Co^{II} complex was observed.

Results and Discussion

The condensation product of anthranilic acid and glyoxal was a mixture of lactone and Schiff base (Scheme 1). The Schiff base was potentially a tetradentate ligand and wrapped around the metal ion giving a planar geometry by coordinating through its two nitrogen and two carboxylate oxygen atoms.

Scheme 1

The lactone ring opens up in presence of a metal ion or in polar solvent and the lactone-Schiff base equilibrium shifts towards left-hand side. To avoid lactone formation the template preparation of the metal complexes was preferred. The complexes prepared *in situ* and that from the metal-ligand mixture were identical.

The solid state ir spectrum of the ligand shows strong sharp ν_{NH} bands at 3330, 2080 and 2900 cm^{-1} which indicate lactone structure. But the presence of Schiff base can not be overruled as there are strong sharp bands at 1500s, 1580s, 1610s and 1710s cm^{-1} which support $-\text{C}=\text{N}-$ bond².

Cobalt complex: When O_2 is bubbled through the DMF solution of the Co^{II} complex (light pink), it absorbs oxygen and turns dark violet. Even when strong ligand like pyridine is present, the oxygen adduct is formed. The ratio of cobalt : O_2 was found to be 1 : 0.48 indicating that approximately half mole of O_2 per mole of the cobalt complex was absorbed and that the oxygenated complex is supposed to be dimeric. The ir spectrum of the oxygenated solid showed a band at 1145 cm^{-1} due to coordinated molecular oxygen³. The Co^{II} -BOBO showed strong bands at 1620, 1595 and 1540 cm^{-1} , suggesting a conjugated double bonded system, and at 1620–1595 cm^{-1} symmetric and asymmetric $\text{C}=\text{N}$ stretching modes. But any assignment⁴ to

uncoupled $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ is unwise in view of the isotopic labelling study that indicates extensive vibrational coupling in Schiff bases⁵. The significant frequency shift of these bands upon complexation of BOBO does indeed suggest vibrational coupling of $-\text{C}=\text{N}-$ and $-\text{C}=\text{C}-$ stretching frequencies. Bands at 410 at 325 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu_{\text{N}-\text{O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{N}}$ respectively.

The electronic spectra of the cobalt(II) complex show low intensity bands at 542 ($\epsilon=125$), 480 ($\epsilon=178$), 428 ($\epsilon=260$) and 380 nm ($\epsilon=645$) both in the solid state and in non-donor solvent. This indicates that the complex has similar structure in solid state and in solution. These values are similar to the previously reported data⁶ for square-planar cobalt(II) complexes. The magnetic moment of this complex is 2.34 B.M., which is well within the range (2.1–2.9 B.M.) for low-spin square-planar Co^{II} complexes. This is attributed to one unpaired electron and some orbital contribution.

Cobalt complex with pyridine and its oxygen adduct: The mono-pyridine adduct is a violet complex and insoluble in THF, CH_2Cl_2 and chloroform. This complex shows two broad bands around 640 ($\epsilon=434$), 470 nm ($\epsilon=500$) and a sharp band at 362 nm ($\epsilon=1843$).

The magnetic moment of PyCoBOBO is 2.51 B.M. and is well within the range (2.1–2.9 B.M.) of a rectangle pyramidal complex. Since the complex is pentacoordinated and the BOBO has a planar array of two nitrogens and two oxygen atoms, the formation of tetrahedral geometry is precluded due to less flexibility in the $\text{C}-\text{C}$ chain. The result of the present investigation shows a five-coordinate stereochemistry resulting from bonding to cobalt atom of the tetradentate BOBO ligand and of a pyridine molecule in an apical position. The coordination polyhedron of the cobalt atom is well presented by a rectangular based pyramid.

In $\text{Co}(\text{Salen})(\text{Py})$ complex, Calligaris⁷ reported displacement of cobalt out of plane due to inter-ligand repulsion between $\text{C}-\text{C}$ chain of ethylene bridge and the pyridine molecule lying parallel to it. But in this case since the $\text{C}-\text{C}$ chain is linked to two nitrogen atoms through double bonds rendering the whole molecule planar. The introduction of pyridine in axial position will not develop any strain in equatorial plane and the geometry of the chelate remains a rectangular based pyramidal.

This may be due to compromise between participation of cobalt electrons in the π -molecular orbitals delocalised on the equatorial ligand and the best σ -overlap in the cobalt apical ligand bond.

The pyridine adduct is a good oxygen-sensitive complex. It absorbs oxygen when exposed to air or oxygen is bubbled through its solution in pyridine and turns dark violet.

It has been suggested that because of the interaction of the electrons of the conjugate system of the equatorial ligand with the electrons of the metal atoms to give π -molecular orbitals, molecular oxygen

can be absorbed easily if a σ -donor or a Lewis base is bonded in an axial position to increase the availability of electrons on the metal atom. The metal center should have enough charge density to bind the oxygen molecule. The oxygen adduct exhibits two bands around 560 ($\epsilon=138$) and 470 nm ($\epsilon=200$) and are suggestive for an octahedral geometry. These transitions are assigned as ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4E_g(P)$, respectively. The broadening of these bands is attributed to distortion from regular octahedral geometry. The magnetic moment of this complex is 5.12 B.M. which also supports octahedral geometry.

The imidazole adduct in pyridine shows two broad bands at 505 ($\epsilon=624$), 560 nm ($\epsilon=580$) and two shoulders at 480 ($\epsilon=540$) and 640 nm ($\epsilon=323$). The transitions assigned are ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4E_g(P)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}(P)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, respectively. These assignments are consistent with those given for octahedral haloacetate complexes of cobalt(II). The magnetic moment of this complex is 5.01 B.M. which suggests a high-spin distorted octahedral geometry.

The nickel complex (NiBOBO) is diamagnetic. The diamagnetism is very strong indication that the spatial arrangement of the ligand molecule around the nickel ion is square-planar. The other preferred orientation should give the value of the magnetic moment corresponding to two unpaired electrons.

Electronic spectrum of the nickel complex shows three bands at 785, 582 and 442 nm; the intensity of the band at 785 nm is comparatively weaker. The band at 442 nm is in the region where $d-d$ transitions peculiar to square-planar nickel(II) are found. For the nickel complex the symmetry has been approximated as D_{4h} . The transitions at 442 and 582 nm are ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{3g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$, respectively.

The complex is highly insoluble in all the common donor and non-donor solvents. These results suggest that unlike salicylaldimine counterparts the complex is low-spin square-planar polymeric *trans*-structure and this configuration is retained even in donor solvents such as pyridine *etc.*

Copper(II)-BOBO complex is diamagnetic. The spectrum of this complex shows three bands at 360, 510 and 642 nm; the latter two are assigned to $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ and $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$ transitions, respectively. A

square-planar arrangement of the ligand molecules around copper(II) ion is proposed. Tsuchida and co-workers⁸ showed that in diamagnetic complexes where paramagnetism is partially or completely quenched absorb at 375 nm. In this case we have observed a high intensity band at 360 nm, which may be similar to 375 nm band. The complex is highly insoluble in donor and non-donor solvents suggesting a polymeric structure. Thus the magnetic, visible and ir spectral data suggest a square-planar polymeric *trans*-structure for the copper complex. The spin-spin interaction takes place either of σ - or δ -bond formation or by superexchange phenomenon.

The pyridine adduct of the copper complex has λ_{max} 580 nm ($\epsilon=428$) which suggests a dimer having highly distorted tetragonal geometry⁹.

From these results the bands which appear in the ir spectra of the complexes and which are absent in the free ligand spectra, in the range $410-325\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in case of cobalt(II), $345-325\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in CoBOBO_2 , $410-320\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in CuBOBO and $520-420\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in case of NiBOBO are assigned to ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-N} stretching frequencies, respectively. It is further concluded that NiBOBO complex is having a very stable square-planar geometry but the cobalt(II) and copper(II)-BOBO complexes do change to square-pyramidal and octahedral high-spin complexes on addition of bases at 5th and 6th positions. There is no measurable change due to solvent effect on these complexes.

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